

Ambedkar In the Digital Age: Caste, Gender and Democracy

H.M. Natikar

Assistant Professor, Government First Grade College,
BasavanaBagewadi, Vijayapur.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17804750>

ABSTRACT:

The paper attempts to comprehend the complexities of caste, gender, and democracy by analyzing different aspects of Ambedkar's writings and other related texts. It also aims to uncover the similarities and disparities between digital and physical realities. It has been discovered that, like offline environments, online outlets reflect oppressive and abusive practices against women and marginalized caste groups, and are therefore, with few exceptions, clearly representations of the same real-world phenomena.

KEYWORDS:

Caste, Gender, Democracy, Digitalization, Reconstruction

.....

Introduction:

B. R. Ambedkar, a champion for women and human rights and a leading social reformer, has given a great deal to the world's crucial understanding of democracy, freedom and governance. His conceptualization of the genesis and continuity of the subservience of castes and women is the product of thorough socio-historical analysis and the idea that the quest for human rights and social justice is of great significance and fundamental to a respectful existence. By getting into his understanding of the real world through his writings, this article seeks to explore the reconstruction of caste and gender identities through virtual spaces such as the internet or mass media. The future of democracy, in its entirety, in the digital age, is also being examined.

Methodology:

This study paper provides a narrative analysis of caste, gender, and democracy using secondary information sources and other related materials.

Caste in India: Working Prospects and Change:

Caste is a hierarchical grouping of people in which their mobility of social status is severely restricted. Ambedkar (1917), one of India's most

learned personalities, has excoriated the caste system for lacking any scientific basis for its classification into fixed, watertight compartments that perpetuate graded inequality. Supporters of this system argue that it allows society to function more interdependently. Ambedkar (1917), on the other hand, concluded after a thorough historical examination of various religious and socio-economic texts that caste serves no useful purpose in society, but rather promotes corruption and exploitation of people. It smothers the public spirit and sense of public charity by advocating responsibility as caste loyalty, resulting in forced exclusion and unfavourable inclusion (Ambedkar, 1917; Sen, 2000). Ambedkar (1917) identified the division of castes into different groups as the foundation of privilege and exploitation, and described it as a division of labourers rather than a division of labour because it stifles innovation and fosters distrust between them.

Many modern liberal thinkers believe that caste is evolving in Indian society, and have attributed various aspects of change to it (Kumar, 2014; Jodhka, 2015). The evolution of caste can be seen by listing some of them and grouping them under structural, functional, and attitudinal changes:

1. Structural change: Many believe that structural support for brahmin supremacy has dwindled. With the advancement of educational attainment, and legal and constitutional support, the concepts of equality, liberty, and fraternity gained traction. Special constitutional provisions provided to certain groups of people from the weaker sections of the society under Part XVI have boosted their confidence and provided them with opportunities, as well as enabling them to stand firm against exploitation in some cases.
2. Functional change and change in status fixation: Some believe that occupational flexibility has resulted in a shift in status fixation (Jodhka, 2015). Liberalized constraints and advancement of means of transport and communication have brought intergenerational mobility in education for women and marginalized caste groups. The lifestyle has conflated hygiene rules with caste restrictions, making it easier to maintain caste hierarchy in terms of pure and impure. However, marriage restrictions remain in effect, and any change is met with vehement societal opposition.

3. Attitudinal Change: Ascriptive status benefits only the upper caste elites, not the general public. People in the middle of a shift in attitude towards economic benefits and the exercise of power over others also influenced changes the economic scale, on the other hand, believe in a performance-based hierarchy while maintaining ritual status. As a result, for them, the law of karma and the doctrine of soul transmigration have been diluted by hard work.

Caste discrimination has evolved into a more effect-oriented phenomenon, whereas, the philosophical foundations of caste discrimination continue to be rigidly enforced, even if latently. According to Ambedkar (1917), caste has its genesis and perpetuation in patriarchal control over women and marriage choices. As a result, caste has never been free of women's exploitation. With few exceptions, patriarchal forces continue to hold women captive, and the freedom to choose one's marriage partner, which is a personal and private matter, is heavily influenced by cultural dictations and religious sanctions.

Gender and Patriarchy: Interrelated Evolutionism

Gender is a social construct that divides people into sexes, each with their own set of social roles. Sexuality has always been seen as a gateway to culture, and cultural dispositions have always dominated this realm. Consequently, patriarchy emerged as a result of dominance over sexual desires. The purpose was also to give control of property rights to a small group of people in a closed circle with caste and ethnic boundaries (Ambedkar, 1917; Rodrigues, 2002).

Gender roles are also defined as the ascriptive status of sexes within the binary of men and women. This has been used to draw dividing lines between the sexes, with females assigned to unpaid care work and described as emotional and weak, in need of male protection. Outside work was something that men reserved for themselves. Therefore, there is a complex and interconnected evolutionism between gender and patriarchy.

Caste and gender construction also share a lot of similarities in terms of social role allocation, private and public space engagement, occupational boundaries, marriage restrictions, property rights, and socio-ritual privileges. Gender has only two divisions, caste has four, excluding untouchables, and there are many more subdivisions in the hierarchical orders. Both caste and gender discrimination, on the other hand, is a

pattern-oriented phenomenon with the presumption of superiority and inferiority, as well as marginalization as an effect. As a result, caste and gender are intertwined aspects that define some groups' privileges while marginalizing others.

Caste and Gender: Digital Reflections

Digital sociality is fostering virtual human interaction and socialization in today's world, which is dominated by communication and networking grids. Friendships, relationships, marriages, and other social connections are all pronounced and carried out by the use of social media sites. However, the online world, like the physical world, is not immune to power dynamics, and digital networks have once again become a reflection of socioeconomic inequality and marginalization.

In the case of gender abuse, multiple threats and offensive language appear on social media platforms on a daily basis in an attempt to silence women's voices in developing countries like India. This not only works against the person to whom it may be addressed, but it also sends a message that men are superior to other sexes in positions of authority. Women's socio-historical disadvantages have a detrimental effect on their share of benefits in modern society as well. Women's virtual movement in the online realm is regulated by their digital engagement, as the movement of women in traditional societies was restricted in order to control their choices, especially sexuality, resulting in a large gender digital divide in men's favour (Kumar, 2018).

Furthermore, the role of family in one's friendship remains intact, reinforcing the notion of same-gender friendship, and it's difficult to allow friendship between people of different genders, even online, without attaching any negative connotations to it. And if it does happen, it will be subjected to a variety of restrictions. True, fear of being watched has harmed the psychological and emotional wellbeing of the younger generation more than anything else. Resistance to patriarchal subjugation and inequality has, on the other hand, made a way through online media channels, as seen in the #MeToo movement. However, only a limited number of people are able to tackle the social stigma and come forward to speak freely about their experiences of exploitation and violence.

Another factor that has been expressed heavily on digital platforms is caste. Today, economic, educational, and occupational statuses play a

significant role in digital relationships. However, the core conditions for any involvement are still religious, ritual, and social, with caste identities playing a major role. As much of the space is occupied and dominated by upper caste elites, the digitalization of caste has diversified its connotation and ill effects. Numerous online communities, many of which are based on caste affiliations are very easy to find today. Although digital caste is as diverse as elitism today, ritual foundations are at the core of choices and preferences, not only in recruitment but also in relationships with friends, mates, and spouses. Online dating apps and marriage websites can be used to investigate the dynamics of marriage and the associated caste preferences. While talking about caste choices in love and marriages, Dr. Dhar, a women's studies professor at the University of Michigan, asks, "How many love marriages do we know of between Brahmins and Dalits?," in her latest

Collection of essays (Kirpal, 2020).

Boywad (2020), studied different patterns of relationships, such as friendship and love, while researching at the JNU campus in New Delhi, and noticed that 'love' could also be a social construction in which questions about caste, class, and gender arise when choosing a romantic partner. Technology has also been identified as one of the most important interventions in providing information about one's identity. As a result, endogamous marriages have found a new home on digital platforms in order to maintain caste.

Future of Democracy and Digital Marginalization

Ambedkar's vision of democracy and his ideal of a 'good society' were inextricably linked. One of the important aspects of Ambedkar's democratic vision was that it was geared towards social transformation and human progress. He considered 'liberty, equality, and fraternity' to be essential elements of a good society (Idiculla, 2017).

Democracy is significant not only in terms of politics, but also in terms of socio, cultural, economic, and other aspects. For one to be able to engage effectively and thereby in every element of the democratic setup, social democracy is absolutely important (Rodrigues, 2002). However, the two most prominent forms of social agency, caste and gender, do not bring democratic inclusion into the picture. Caste and gender are both based on the idea of a power hierarchy. As a result, if any participation is given to

women and marginalized caste groups, it will not have the same influence over decisions as dominant forces such as higher caste status and male privileges.

The virtual media world, where participation was ostensibly free and democratic, once again reflects real-world power relations in myriad guises. The following are some of the major outlines that characterize the undemocratic digital setup:

1. **Participation limitations:** In India, digital penetration is inequitable. Not only the economic capital but cultural and social affiliations also influence the digital reach and activity. Most of the Indian digital users are also not the creators of contents rather they are the passive consumers of services and information provided through that platform.
2. **Digitalization:** A political rhetoric in India: Rather a socio-economic intervention, digitalization has gained acceleration in recent past for political reasons. Since there is so little way to verify their authenticity, fake truths, often with political agendas, have become dominant in shaping reality over online platforms. As a result, what appears to be public opinion is simply the viewpoint of the online platform's dominant players, who can exploit and manipulate it according to their own interests.
3. **Increasing political atrocities and degrading voices of dissent:** When the number of online passive consumers grows, so does the threat of dissenting voices, especially against big corporations, technocrats, and political figures. As a result, using power and state repressive agents to muzzle dissenting voices may become another means of suppressing freedom of expression. It induces a symbolic fear of actively being online. This causes psychological discomfort for the dissenting voices which results in an undemocratic condition in which facts can be understood but not expressed or explained to others.
4. **Economic compulsion and inequitable benefits:** The benefits of the online economy are not equal for everyone. Those who can afford to switch to the digital economy enjoy the greatest benefits. Small businesses and others who are not well-versed in technical know-how, on the other hand, face hindered choices. This can also lead to online fraud, which causes significant damage to people who are on

the margins.

5. Life chances of people: "Life chances" is a probabilistic concept that defines the possibility of a person's life turning out a certain way in particular circumstances (Kumar, 2018). Socioeconomic factors influence digital outcomes and women and marginalized caste groups are often excluded from digital platforms for a variety of reasons, one of which is 'violence', which can take the form of verbal, sexual, or physical abuse. Furthermore, although online education offers content, it does not inspire learners to engage in critical thinking. All of this restricts their public participation and establishes a cyclicity of marginalization for them, limiting their prospects and lowering their life chances.

Conclusion:

The function of democracy, according to Ambedkar, is to serve the interests of society as a whole, rather than any particular class, caste, or group. Repression and abuse of a group or underprivileged people in any way, he believes, is the antithesis of democracy and humanism. However, much as in the real world, digital media platforms have become a public space of violence and repression of voices of women and oppressed caste groups. As a result, despite appearing to be free and decentralized, the digital media are once again monopolized by those in positions of power. Therefore, much more needs to be done to seriously address the problem of digital violence and marginalization, and research emphasis and vision, as well as effective policy initiatives, are needed in this field.

References:

1. Ambedkar, B. R. (1917). Castes in India: Their Mechanism, Genesis and Development. Indian Antiquary,46.
2. Boywad, B. (2020, August 09). The caste complex: Is JNU really a love haven? The Indian Express.<https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/caste-jnu-love-dating-dalit-6546446/> (Accessed on 21stMarch, 2021).
3. Idiculla, M. (2017, April 22). Ambedkar's Vision of Democracy. The New Indian express.<https://www.newindianexpress.com/opinions/2017/apr/22/ambedkars-vision-of-democracy-1596282.html> (Accessed on March 21, 2021).
4. Jodhka, S. S. (2015). Caste in Contemporary India. New Delhi: Routledge.
5. Kirpal, N. (2020, September 26). From caste on Tinder to Love Jihad, the complex facets of love in India.Money control. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/trends/from-caste-on-tinder-to-love-jihad-thecomplex-facets-of-love-in-india-5886551.html> (Accessed on March 21, 2021).
6. Kumar, A. (2018). Women's Participation in New Digital India: A Critical Overview. Women's Link,24(4), 2-8.
7. Kumar, V. (2014). Situating Dalits in Indian Sociology. In Judge, P. S. (ed.) Towards Sociology of Dalits.New Delhi: Sage Publications.
8. Rodrigues, V. (ed.) (2002). The Essential Writings of B. R. Ambedkar. UK: Oxford University Press.
9. Sen, A. (2000). Social Exclusion: Concept, Application and Scrutiny. Social Development Paper No. 1.

Funding:

This study was not funded by any grant.

Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

About the License:

© The Authors 2024. The text of this article is open access and licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.